

Research Article

Evaluation of Treatment Effectiveness Using Patient Satisfaction with Acupuncture's Results

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Abstract

Objective: This study investigated the feasibility of using the level of patient satisfaction to evaluate the effectiveness of acupuncture, which is a treatment with an effectiveness that is difficult to evaluate objectively.

Subjects: Subjects were 741 patients who underwent acupuncture by the lead author and who responded that "it had an effect".

Methods: All of the responders who underwent 6 consecutive sessions, in principle one session per week, were asked to rate their "level of patient satisfaction" on a scale of 0 to 100%. At the same time, they were shown a chart indicating the extent to which symptoms were alleviated and they were asked to select a level from I-V: In regard to bothersome (distressing) symptom, Level I: disappeared, Level II: almost disappeared, Level III: abated considerably, Level IV: abated, and Level V: abated slightly.

Results: Linear regression analysis of patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation of symptoms yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.87. The least-squares regression line was as follows. Y (patient satisfaction) = $-8.7 X$ (level of alleviation) + 106.8 When 1,2,3,4, and 5 were substituted as X values (the level of alleviation) in the least-squares regression line, the Y value (patient satisfaction) was $98.1 \approx 100$, $89.4 \approx 90$, $80.7 \approx 80$, $72.0 \approx 70$, and $63.3 \approx 60$, respectively.

Discussion: Based on these results, levels of patient satisfaction of 100%, 90%, 80%, 70%, and 60% can be considered to correspond to levels of alleviation of symptoms of I, II, III, IV, and V, respectively.

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Conclusion: If a level of patient satisfaction > 60% corresponds to level III alleviation of symptoms (symptoms abated slightly), then a treatment can be considered "effective." If a level of patient satisfaction > 80% corresponds to level V alleviation of symptoms (symptoms abated considerably), then the treatment can be considered "highly effective".

Keywords: Acupuncture; Alleviation of Symptom; Evaluation of Effectiveness; Patient Satisfaction

Introduction

Methods for evaluating a treatment's effectiveness differ depending on the symptoms or condition being treated. When objective data are obtained, effectiveness can easily be evaluated, such as measuring body temperature to evaluate the efficacy of an antipyretic or measuring the amount of nasal discharge to evaluate a treatment's effectiveness in treating acute rhinitis. When measuring objective data is difficult, however, various approaches are used. With a treatment to reduce pain, as an example, pain intensity is typically evaluated using pain scales or face scales [1], such as the VAS, VRS, and NRS [2-10]. However, problems remain in terms of interpreting scores based on the type of pain and in evaluating changes in pain intensity before and after treatment. Hot flashes are a menopausal symptom, and the frequency of hot flashes occurring per day is used as an indicator of a treatment's effectiveness. However, this does not allow evaluation of their severity or the extent to which symptoms are alleviated. Questionnaires like the SRS-18 are used to evaluate the psychological symptoms of Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS). The extent of a decrease in score after treatment can be determined, but the extent to which the primary complaint is alleviated remains unclear [11]. When administering Kampo treatment and acupuncture, obtaining objective measurements of symptoms such as neck/shoulder stiffness, dizziness, nausea, indigestion, frozen shoulder, and acne is often difficult. The current study investigated the feasibility of using the level of patient satisfaction after treatment to evaluate acupuncture's effectiveness in treating certain symptoms in routine practice. If the level of patient satisfaction can be used to evaluate a treatment's effectiveness, then it can presumably be used to uniformly evaluate the treatment's effectiveness in treating every symptom, without worrying about specific methods of evaluating individual symptoms. Using the level of patient satisfaction to evaluate a treatment's effectiveness has already been attempted with treatment satisfaction questionnaires (TSQs), but those questionnaires are complex and the resulting scores on them are not fully accurate [12-16]. To create a simple evaluation system with a concise questionnaire, steps must be taken to align the extent to which symptoms are alleviated and the level of patient satisfaction.

Subjects and Methods

Subjects were 741 patients who underwent acupuncture by the lead author from September 2019 to May 2025 and who responded that "it had an effect." Patients undergoing other treatments for the symptoms in question were excluded.

Acupuncture was done using disposable acupuncture needles (No2, dia. 0.18 mm × length 40 mm, Seirin Corporation, Tokyo) with a guide tube, and the needles were inserted only slightly and gently tapped into place. In other words, the needle protruded from the guide tube, and each needle was inserted only slightly and tapped into place without penetrating deep into tissue. The combinations of acupuncture points used were determined by the lead author based on symptoms [17-21]. After insertion, needles were left in place for 15 min. In this study, acupuncture was performed solely by the lead author. Patients who underwent 6 consecutive sessions, in principle one session per week, were asked “Did it have an effect?” one week after the final session. All of the patients who answered “Yes” were then asked to rate their “level of patient satisfaction” on a scale of 0 to 100%. At the same time, they were shown a chart indicating the extent to which symptoms were alleviated and they were asked to select a level of alleviation of bothersome (distressing) symptoms from I-V: Level I, disappeared; Level II, almost disappeared; Level III, abated considerably; Level IV, abated; and Level V, abated slightly.

Treatment started only after informed consent to participate in this study was obtained from subjects in writing. The correlation between patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation was statistically analyzed using linear regression.

Patient information was extracted from electronic medical records and consisted only of treatment details and the patient's initials and the patient's age so that individuals could not be identified. This information was securely stored. This study was approved by the bioethics review board of this facility (Approval No: MMYC_2026-03-01).

Results

The relationship between patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation of symptoms (Table 1) is shown in table 2. Of the total patients, 88.5% were responders. The largest proportion of patients with level I of alleviation was patients with 100% satisfaction. Similarly, the largest proportion of patients with level II alleviation was patients with 90s% satisfaction, the largest proportion of patients with level III alleviation was those with 80s% satisfaction, the largest proportion of patients with level IV alleviation was those with 70s% satisfaction, and the largest proportion of patients with level V alleviation was those with 60s% satisfaction.

Bothersome (distressing) symptoms	
I	Disappeared
II	Almost disappeared
III	Abated considerably
IV	Abated
V	Abated slightly

Table 1: Summary of the extent to which symptoms were alleviated, classified into 5 levels.

Linear regression analysis of patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation of symptoms yielded a correlation coefficient of 0.87, and a scatter diagram is shown in figure 1. The least-squares regression line was as follows. Y (patient satisfaction) = $-8.7 X$ (level of alleviation) + 106.8.

To plot the level of alleviation of symptoms in a scatter diagram, the numbers 1,2,3,4, and 5 were used in place of I, II, III, IV, and V, respectively.

Level of Alleviation	Patient Satisfaction	Total Number	Number	Proportion	
				Number	Proportion
I	100%	189	99	61.10%	92.60%
	90s%		76	40.20%	
	80s%		14	8.60%	
	70s%		0	0	
	60s%		0	0	
	50s%		0	0	
II	100%	159	32	20.10%	98.70%
	90s%		91	57.20%	
	80s%		34	21.40%	
	70s%		2	1.30%	
	60s%		0	0	
	50s%		0	0	
III	100%	158	0	0	98.70%
	90s%		17	10.80%	
	80s%		119	75.30%	
	70s%		20	12.70%	
	60s%		2	1.30%	
	50s%		0	0	
IV	100%	148	3	2.00%	92.60%
	90s%		8	5.40%	
	80s%		14	9.50%	
	70s%		96	64.90%	
	60s%		27	18.20%	
	50s%		0	0	
V	100%	87	0	0	97.70%
	90s%		0	0	
	80s%		2	2.30%	
	70s%		9	10.30%	
	60s%		73	83.90%	
	50s%		3	3.40%	

Table 2: Relationship between the level of patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation of symptoms.

By symptom treated, patient satisfaction with acupuncture was as follows (in decreasing order): lower back pain: 95.2%, knee pain: 91.0%, frozen shoulder: 89.1%, neck/shoulder stiffness: 87.4%, anxiety/palpitations: 86.9%, premenstrual syndrome: 86.3%, headaches: 85.3%, dysmenorrhea: 84.8%, dizziness: 84.8%, and other symptoms.

Figure 1: Scatter plot of the relationship between patient satisfaction and the level of alleviation.

Discussion

As shown in figure 1, patient satisfaction was closely correlated with the level of alleviation of symptoms according to linear regression analysis.

Findings from tables 1 and 2 were as follows. Of the patients with level I of alleviation, 92.6% reported a level of satisfaction over 90%. Of the patients with level II alleviation, 98.7% reported a level satisfaction around 90% (80-100%). Of the patients with level III alleviation, 98.7% reported a level satisfaction around 80% (70-100%). Of the patients with level IV alleviation, 92.6% reported a level of satisfaction around 70% (60-90%). Of the patients with level V alleviation, 97.7% reported a level of satisfaction around 60% (50-80%).

Linear regression analysis indicated that patient satisfaction was closely correlated with the level of alleviation of symptoms. When 1,2,3,4, and 5 were substituted as X values (the level of alleviation) in the least-squares regression line, the Y value (patient satisfaction) was 98.1~100, 89.4~90, 80.7~80, 72.0~70, and 63.3~60, respectively.

Thus, levels of patient satisfaction of 100%, 90%, 80%, 70%, and 60% can be considered to correspond to levels of alleviation of symptoms of I, II, III, IV, and V, respectively.

If, based on these findings, "symptoms abated slightly" can be interpreted to mean that treatment was "effective," then a level of satisfaction of 60% or higher can be interpreted to mean that treatment was "effective." And if "symptoms abated considerably" can be interpreted to mean that treatment was "highly effective," then a level of satisfaction of 80% or higher can be interpreted to mean that treatment was "highly effective."

An advantage of using the level of patient satisfaction to evaluate a treatment's effectiveness is that it directly measures satisfaction resulting from treatment. Of the patients with a 100% level of satisfaction in this study, 23.9% reported that symptoms were alleviated, but not to the extent that "symptoms disappeared." This means that there are patients who are sufficiently satisfied with a treatment even when it is not entirely effective, potentially leading to overestimation. Patients whose symptoms did not "disappear for the most part" with a prior treatment may have had their symptoms disappear for the most part with a given treatment, and they may have been discounted. Conversely, of the patients with a level of satisfaction around 60%, 26.2% reported that their symptoms were alleviated to the extent that "symptoms abated." Nonetheless, they would be grouped in with patients whose "symptoms abated slightly." This is presumably due to high expectations of a treatment's effectiveness. The findings from this study are applicable not only to acupuncture but also to situations where evaluation of a treatment's effectiveness using objective measurements is impossible. Expectations of physicians and communication between patients and physicians could be forms of bias that affect a patient's level of satisfaction. In the current study, however, treatment was provided by the same physician, so differences in communication due to the treating physician were eliminated. A placebo effect due to the expectations against different physicians providing treatment was also eliminated [22-26]. When patients complained of multiple symptoms, their level of satisfaction may reflect not only the extent to which their primary complaint was alleviated but also that their other symptoms were alleviated. In the current study, acupuncture to treat various symptoms resulted in a high level of patient satisfaction. The method of evaluating a treatment's effectiveness

using patient satisfaction as was described in this study may be useful for treatments with effectiveness that cannot be evaluated based on objective measurements despite high levels of patient satisfaction.

Conclusion

If a level of patient satisfaction > 60% corresponds to level III alleviation of symptoms (symptoms abated slightly), then a treatment can be considered "effective." If a level of patient satisfaction > 80% corresponds to level V alleviation of symptoms (symptoms abated considerably), then the treatment can be considered "highly effective."

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